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Effects of Combination of Plant Extracts for the Control of Black Bean Aphids and Other Beneficial Insects on Common Beans

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4.0 Abstract

An experiment was conducted during wet and dry seasons at Ndugutu village from December, 2020 to August, 2021 to investigate effects of combinations of three selected pesticidal plants for the control of Black Bean Aphids (BBAs) and their effects on beneficial insects on common bean crop (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L). The experimental design was Randomized Complete Block Design with three replications. The combinations of pesticidal plant species extracts of *D. trifoliata*, *D. ambrosioides* and *V. amygdalina* (DT: DA: VA), *D. trifoliata* and *D. ambrosioides* (DT: DA), *D. trifoliata* and *V. amygdalina* (DT: VA) and *D. ambrosioides* and *V. amygdalina* (DA: VA) each with 200 g/L of water. Results show that there was a significant difference ($F = 4.26$, $df = 5, 204$, $p = 0.0001$) amongst different treatments. All combinations were as effective as synthetic pesticide against BBAs during wet season while mixture of *D. trifoliata*, *D. ambrosioides* and *V. amygdalina* (DT: DA: VA) and *D. trifoliata* and *V. amygdalina* (DT: VA) were the second most effective preceded by synthetic pesticide during dry season. In addition, there was a significant difference of treatments ($F = 2.81$, $df = 5, 204$, $p = 0.039$) on bean yields. The highest bean yield during wet and dry season was recorded in synthetic pesticide with mean average of (1127.8 and 1786.6) kg/ha respectively. The second highest bean yields were recorded on treatment combinations of DT: DA and DT: DA: VA with a mean average of 955.3 and 1150.2) kg/ha respectively. This research has demonstrated that combination of pesticidal plants can be as effective as synthetic pesticide for the control of BBAs. Therefore, should be made to their incorporation in IPM in Tanzania.

Keywords: Pesticidal plants, Synthetic pesticides, black bean aphids, incidence and severity, yield, beneficial insects and common bean

4.1 Introduction

Crop insect pest control from pesticidal plants is growing without clear benefits and consequences on environment and non-target organisms Isman and Grieneisen (2013) However, Stevenson *et al.* (2017) reported that there are many plant species which are known for chemistry and efficacy that could be used as pesticidal plants. Isman (2017) reported that as the demand for the use of pesticidal plants by the farmers is increasing, research is required to understand how diverse of botanical plants work under various environmental conditions.

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Pesticidal plants contain poisonous amalgams derivative from secondary metabolites used to make plant spiteful to insects, to attract insects to poison them and they are environmental friendly (Isman, 2016; Mpumi *et al.*, 2016). There are various pesticidal plant species that has chemical compounds which offers useful biological substances for the control of various crop insect pests. For instance, Green *et al.* (2017); Tembo *et al.* (2018); Degri *et al.* (2012) reported that *Vernonia amygdalina* to contain sesquiterpene lactones, vernolide and vernadol which have insecticidal activities against various field insect pests. Moreover, Pavela *et al.* (2017) reported that *Dysphania ambrosioides* contain chemical compounds such as (flavonoids, saponins, terpenes, sterols, and alkaloids which used also to control numerous crop insect pests. Additionally, *Derris trifoliata* is one of the broad spectrum pesticidal plant which contains rotenone a chemical compound which is a contact and stomach poison against crop insect pests (El - Wakeil, 2013). For successfully control of insect pests, it is essential to ensure frequency monitoring and spraying regime of pesticidal plant extracts.

Although synthetic pesticides have been commonly used to control insect pests, they have been testified to have several impact on non-target insects, environment and insect pest resistance to pesticide dosage (Raghavendra *et al.*, 2016; Moshi and Matoju, 2017). Results have indicated that continuous use of a single pesticide dosage for the control of insect pests may develop an insect to pesticide resistance and may become difficult to control using the same synthetic pesticide (Campos *et al.*, 2015; Roditakis *et al.*, 2018; Campos *et al.*, 2017).

Therefore, to prevent insects from becoming resistant from a given similar pesticide dosage, Ullah *et al.* (2017) and Yu and Ting (2019) reported that mixture of different synthetic pesticides may result into more effective insect pest control. Nevertheless, there are few studies on the use of combined pesticidal plants in controlling insect pests in crops. For instance, Subedi *et al.* (2018) reported that combination of botanical leaf extract of *Falconeria insignis*, *Agave americana*, *Acorus calamus*, *Nicotiana tabacum* and *Melia azedarach* was effective on the reduction of Black Bean Aphids. Additionally, Kummar *et al.* (2007) reported also that a combination of *Azadirachta indica* and *Millettia pinnata* extract is highly effective against aphids and mites. Likewise, Pavela and Benelli (2016) argued that mixture of terpenes from different plant species they play an important role in plant defense against different crop pest.

Moreover, apart from controlling field Black Bean Aphids, other reserchers used mixture of pesticidal plants to control storage and field insect pests for instance, Musa *et al.* (2007) reported that when *Vernonia amygdalina* mixed with *Ocimum. gratissimum* at equal proportion reduced abundance of bean bruchid. Furthermore, Emeasor *et al.* (2007) acknowledged that mixture of seed powder of *Piper guineense* and *Thevetia peruviana* reduced oviposition and adult emergence of *Callosobruchus maculatus*. Shazia *et al.* (2006) found that a combination of *Azadirachta indica* and *Tephrosia vogelii* were effective in the control of cowpea seed bruchid (*C. maculatus*). Additionally, Also, Rayhan *et al.* (2014) reported that mixture of *Azadirachta indica* with *Swietenia mahagoni* were capable to inhibit seed damage by rice weevil in storage.

Therefore, this study was conducted to determine efficacy of four different combinations of pesticidal plant species of *D. trifoliata*, *D. ambrosioides* and *V. amygdalina* (DT: DA: VA), *D. trifoliata* and *D. ambrosioides* (DT: DA), *D. trifoliata* and *V. amygdalina* (DT: VA) and *D. ambrosioides* and *V. amygdalina* (DA: VA) as an alternative to conventional pesticide for two seasons for the control of insect pests on field while safeguarding nature of the environment.

4.2 Materials and Methods

4.2.1 Description of experimental site

This study was carried out in Mvomero district in Morogoro Region in Tanzania at Ndugutu village (Figure 4.1). The experiment was commenced from December, 2020 to August, 2021. Ndugutu village lies between latitudes of 7°5'33.8"S and longitudes of 37°34'22.7" E with elevation of 1625 m.a.s.l which receives bimodal rainfall patterns ranging from 800- 1600 mm per annum with a mean temperature ranging

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from 18°C to 26°C. The short rains start from November to February while long rain are between March to April (Hashim *et al.*, 2018).

Figure 4.1: Map of part of Morogoro showing village where the study was conducted

4.2.2 Sources of bean Seed, botanicals and synthetic pesticide

Kipapri common bean was used in this experiment because it is the most preferred genotype because of its characteristics of high yield, palatable, high weight and fast cook ability. Pesticidal aqueous solution from Spiny coriander (*D. ambrosioides*), Bitter tea vernonia (*V. amygdalina*) and three leaf derris (*D. trifoliata*) were applied for the control of Black bean aphids. Synthetic pesticide as positive control and was bought from Agro dealers in Morogoro Municipal while plots without application of any chemical were treated as a negative control.

4.2.3 Preparation of pesticidal plants leaf aqueous solution

Fresh leaves from *D. ambrosioides*, *V. amygdalina* and *D. trifoliata* were picked out from nearby villages where the study was conducted and weighed to get 200 g of each plant species. The weighed leaves were mixed together into the same container with all three botanicals at first while the rest were mixed by excluding one of the botanicals for each in a separate container. Pesticidal plants were crushed into even small size less than 0.5mm to increase surface area for extraction efficiency of a required chemical compounds (Chuo *et al.*, 2022). The mixture was soaked in three and two liters of water to make four concentration of 200 g/L of different combinations (DT: DA: VA, DT: DA, DT: VA and DA: VA). According to Anjarwalla *et al.* (2016), water was used as a universal solvent to extract the required materials from selected pesticidal plants. Two milliliter of Potash based soap was added in each liter of solution to aid in extraction of chemical compound and as adjuvant (Kaputa *et al.*, 2015). Each combined concentration of pesticidal aqueous solution was soaked for 24 hours in a tight covered container under ambient condition. The solution was filtered using muslin cloth. One milliliter of IMIDA C344SE (Active ingredient; Cypermethrin 144 g/L + Imidacloprid 200 g/ L) per 1liter of water at application rate of 0.5L/ ha was used as a positive control and without application of any pesticide was treated as a negative control. Pesticidal extracts were prepared each time of application early in the morning or late in the afternoon in order to avoid

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photo degradation nature of pesticidal plant extracts (Onunkun, 2012). The prepared concentrations at every 15 days' interval of application were immediately sprayed following filtering after 24 hours using 1 liter hand sprayer after 30 days since sowing and was repeated three times.

4.2.4 Experimental design

An experiment was laid in Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with six treatments (Table 4.1)

Table 4.1: Treatment structure

Botanicals	Concentration
<i>Derris trifoliata</i> : <i>Dysphania</i> . <i>Ambrosioides</i> : <i>Vernonia amygdalina</i>	DTDAVA; 1:1:1
<i>Derris trifoliata</i> : <i>Dysphania ambrosioides</i>	DTDA; 1:1
<i>Derris trifoliata</i> : <i>Vernonia amygdalina</i>	DTVA; 1:1
<i>Dysphania ambrosioides</i> : <i>Vernonia amygdalina</i>	DAVA; 1:1
Positive Control	PC
Negative Control	NC

DT: DA: VA; 1:1:1; Concentration of 200g/L of each botanical

DT: DA; 1:1; Concentration of 200g/L of each botanical

DT: VA; 1:1; Concentration of 200g/L of each botanical

DA: VA; 1:1; Concentration of 200g/L of each botanical

PC; One milliliter IMIDA C344SE and NC; Without application any chemical

4.3 Data Collection

4.3.1 Abundance of aphids and beneficial insects

Number of aphids were counted from six randomly selected plants from second plant subsequently every fourth plant in third middle rows inside the 4m² in each plot at 5 and 10 days from 5 cm apical twig of sample plant before the next spraying, this is a newly growing part of the plot where most of aphids prefer. Incidence of Black bean aphids was recorded as either zero (0) for absence or one (1) for presence of aphids and then expressed as percentage of plants with aphids over total number of plants sampled in each plot. Aphid count for damage and severity was done by visual inspection and by using magnifying hand lens (x30-21mm) as designed by El Fakhouri *et al.* (2021). Number of aphids per plot of 4m² for the whole plots were recorded for their abundance and severity of damage in a weekly basis by using scale of 0 - 5 as described by Wosula (2016); Mkenda *et al.* (2015).

Table 4.2: Abundance and severity scoring scale

Abundance	Severity of damage (%)
1 = 1- 150	1 = 1-5
2 = 151 - 300	2 = 6 -25
3 = 301 – 450	3 = 26 -50
4 = 451 - 600	4 = 51 -75
5 = Over 601	5 = 75 -100

The lowest abundance ranging from one to over 601 were used to denote the low to high level of aphid's abundance and percentage ranging from one to 100 denote low to high severity of damage of aphids.

4.3.2 Beneficial insects

Yellow and green colour pan traps and pitfall traps were used to capture the number of beneficial insects. Sampling methods per trap were collected based on their species level in each plot as described by Awal *et al.* (2015). A yellow and green plastic dish of 6 cm height and 12 cm diameter having a mixture of water with 2% mild detergent which breaks the surface tension of the water were placed above the ground level. A total of one hundred twenty-six yellow and green pan traps were used in two experimental units. The traps were set weekly in two replicates in each plot for a period of 24 hours. Flying insects landing on the surface of the water in the traps were trapped, collected and preserved in a small plastic bottle filled to half with 70% ethanol for both methods.

Similarly, a small plastic container 10 cm width and 18 cm deep were used as a pitfall traps, two traps were placed in each plot and mouth of each pot was kept at the ground level so as to obstruct insect movement. A total of 126 pitfall traps were used for two experimental units. The pitfall traps were set weekly in replicates for a period of 24 hours. Trapping was continued until when 60% of beans senescence was attained. The trapped insects were preserved into a small plastic bottle filled to half with 70% ethanol.

4.3.3 Insect species identification

Taxonomic identification of specimens was conducted at Sokoine University of Agriculture Entomology Laboratory (Plate 3.3). Identification of beneficial was done using standard keys using morphological features (Buck *et al.*, 2009; Kirk-Spriggs and Sinclair, 2017; Packer *et al.*, 2007). Identified number of species were counted and recorded.

4.3.4 Common bean yield

Yield of beans per plot was measured after threshing. This was obtained by randomly selecting five plants harvested from the three middle rows per plot. Harvested beans were dried on screen house at SUA for three days. There after weight of beans in gram was calculated and then converted into kg ha^{-1} . Samples of beans were weighed by using Electronic Weighing Scale and measured moisture content of samples by using Sparex Moisture Meter at 12.5% of moisture content. The standardized moisture content was calculated using the following formula.

Beans weight calculation formula;
$$Y = \left[\frac{(100-K)}{(100-12.5)} \right] * J$$

Whereas Y is adjusted weight of sample, J is weight of measured sample (g), K is measured moisture of sample.

4.4 Data analysis

Data collected was subjected to two-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at 5% level of significance using XLSTAT 2015.01.41366 using the following model.

$$Y_{ijk} = (\mu + R_i + \text{Season}) + (RS)_{ijk} + T_{jk} + (S * T)_{ik} + \epsilon_{ijk}$$

Where, μ is the overall mean of all experimental units, R_i is the effect of replication. i th and T_{jk} is the effect of treatment k th and ϵ_{ijk} are random errors that are; normally distributed with mean zero and unknown standard deviation, independent of all the values for all other errors. Significance different between the means of treatments was separated by Least Significance Difference ($LSD_{0.05}$).

4.5 Results

4.5.1 Effects of botanical extracts on abundance, incidence and severity of aphids

Botanicals exhibited a significant difference ($F = 16.42$, $df = 5$, 204 , $p = 0.0001$) on the abundance of Black Bean Aphids, incidence ($F = 38.10$, $df = 5$, 204 , $p = 0.0001$), severity (17.41 , $df = 5$, 204 , $p = 0.0001$)

Among different combinations of pesticidal plant extract, combinations of *D. trifoliata*, *D. ambrosioides* and *amygdalina* (DT: DA: VA) and *D. trifoliata* V. *amygdalina* (DT: VA) and *Derris trifoliata* and *D. ambrosioides* (TD: DA) were the most effective in the reduction of abundance of aphids as compared with DA: VA. Whereas combinations of DT: DA: VA and DT: VA demonstrated the highest effectiveness in reduction of incidence of aphids. In addition, all combinations were effective against severity of aphids with except of combination of DA: VA which was less effective (Table 4.4).

4.5.2 Effects of botanical extracts on abundance of beneficial insects

Botanicals demonstrated a significant difference *C. albiceps* ($F = 2.26$, $df = 5$, 204 , $p = 0.005$).

C. albiceps was the only flower visitor recorded, and highest was noted on negative control and DA: VA while least being recorded on the rest of treatments (Table 4.4).

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However, The result show that there was no significant difference ($F = 1.50$, $df = 5$, 204 , $p=0.190$), in abundance of *C. megacephala*, *S.africa* ($F = 0.46$, $df = 5$, 204 , $p = 0.806$), *S. spilogaster* ($F= 1.11$, $df = 5$, 204 , $p = 0.345$), *B. erythrura* ($F = 0.796$, $df = 5$, 204 , $p = 0.544$), *A. amphitrite* ($F = 0.768$, $df = 5$, 204 , $p = 0.573$), *P. mirabilis* ($F = 0.989$, $df= 5$, 204 , $p = 0.425$) and Others- *A.iphigenia*, *L. sablense*, *L. curtis*, *M. levida*,*S. carnaria*, *C. marginalis*, *L. ampullaceal*, *L. silvarum*, *L. asericata*, *S. bullta*, *C. bezziana*, *S. carnaria* and *L. cuprina* ($F= 0.39$, $df = 5$, 204 , $p = 0.039$).

4.5.3 Effects of season on abundance, incidence and severity of aphids

The result shows that there was a significant difference ($F=90.83$, $df=5$, 204 , $p=0.0001$), in abundance of Black Bean Aphids, incidence ($F=112.58$, $df= 5$, 204 , $p= 0.0001$) and severity ($F= 77.65$, $df = 5$, 204 , $p = 0.0001$).

Results indicated that population of aphids, incidence and severity was higher during dry season as compared with wet season (Table 4.4). Negative control revealed to have the highest abundance of aphids, incidence and severity whereas the lowest abundance was recorded on synthetic pesticide during two seasons.

4.5.4 Effects of season on abundance of beneficial insects

The result show that there was a significant difference ($F = 3.96$, $df = 5$, 204 , $p =0.048$) in abundance of *C. albiceps*, *B. erythrura* ($F = 8.73$, $df = 5$, 204 , $p = 0.003$), *C. megacephala* ($F= 6.55$, $df = 5$, 204 , $p = 0.011$), *A. amphitrite* ($F = 15.84$, $df = 5$, 204 , $p = 0.0001$), *S. africa* ($F = 20.26$, $df = 5$, 204 , $p = 0.0001$), *S. spilogaster* ($F = 18.09$, $df= 5$, 204 , $p = 0.0001$) and Others i.e. *A. iphigenia*, *L. sablense*, *L. curtis*, *M. levida*, *S. carnaria*, *C. marginalis*, *L. ampullaceal*, *L. silvarum*, *L. asericata*, *S. bullata*, *C. bezziana*, *S. carnaria* and *L. cuprina* ($F= 8.14$, $df = 5$, 204 , $p = 0.005$).

On other hand, higher abundance of beneficial insects was depicted during wet season as compared with dry season (Table 4.3). Amongst other beneficial insects most abundant were recorded during wet season compared with dry season.

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Table 4.3: Effect of botanicals and season on the Abundance, incidence and severity of aphids

Season	Aphids	Incidence	Severity	<i>C.albiceps</i>	<i>C.megacrphala</i>	<i>S.africa</i>	<i>S.spilogaster</i>	<i>B.erythrura</i>	<i>A.amphitrite</i>	Others
Wet	2.24	14.26	0.41	0.19	0.28	0.43	0.56	0.14	0.65	0.89
Dry	15.75	41.48	1.01	0.05	0.01	0.04	0.14	0.02	0.16	0.45
LSD _{0.05}	2.794	5.059	0.135	0.138	0.207	0.17	0.193	0.08	0.243	0.301
SE	1.00	1.81	0.05	0.05	0.07	0.06	0.07	0.03	0.09	0.11
P.value	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.048	0.011	0.0001	0.0001	0.003	0.006	0.005
Treatments										
NC	20.89 ^a	61.67 ^a	1.22 ^a	0.33 ^a	0.44	0.31	0.56 ^a	0.167	0.56	1.08 ^a
DA:VA	11.91 ^b	32.22 ^b	0.94 ^b	0.19 ^{ab}	0.19	0.28	0.42 ^{ab}	0.083	0.50	0.94 ^{ab}
DT:DA	8.94 ^{bc}	28.89 ^{bc}	0.69 ^c	0.08 ^b	0.06	0.28	0.33 ^{ab}	0.056	0.47	0.67 ^{abc}
DT:VA	7.03 ^c	22.78 ^{cd}	0.61 ^c	0.08 ^b	0.06	0.22	0.33 ^{ab}	0.056	0.36	0.56 ^{bc}
DT:DA:VA	5.01 ^{cd}	18.33 ^d	0.58 ^c	0.00 ^b	0.06	0.19	0.25 ^{ab}	0.056	0.33	0.39 ^c
PC	0.2 ^d	3.33 ^e	0.19 ^d	0.00 ^b	0.06	0.11	0.19 ^b	0.056	0.19	0.39 ^c
SE	1.74	3.14	0.08	0.09	0.13	0.11	0.12	0.05	0.15	0.19
P.value	0.0001	0.0001	0.001	0.05	0.190	0.806	0.335	0.554	0.573	0.039

Different letters within the same column indicate significant difference at P= 0.05 as determined by Tukey's Test;

PC = Synthetic pesticide, NC = Negative control (Without treatment application), DT: DA: VA = Mixture of *Derris trifoliata*, *Dysphania ambrosioides* and *Vernonia amygdalina*, DT: DA = Mixture of *Derris trifoliata* and *Dysphania ambrosioides*, DT: VA = Mixture of *Derris trifoliata* and *Vernonia amygdalina*, DA: VA = Mixture of *Dysphania ambrosioides* and *Vernonia amygdalina*, SE = Standard error and P. value= Probability value.

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4.5.5 Effects of botanicals and season interaction on abundance, incidence and severity of aphids and beneficial insects

Results revealed a significant difference ($F= 6.74$, $df= 5$, 204 , $p = 0.0001$) on the abundance, of Black Bean Aphids, incidence ($F= 4.26$, $df = 5$, 204 , $p = 0.001$) and severity ($F= 2.97$, $df = 5$, 204 , $p = 0.013$) of an interaction between season and treatments. However, interaction demonstrated no significant effect on *C. megacephala* ($F= 1.65$, $df = 5$, 204 , $p = 0.148$), *C. albiceps* ($F= 1.89$, $df = 5$, 204 , $p = 0.097$), *S. spilogaster* ($F= 1.11$, $df = 5$, 204 , $p = 0.345$), *S. africa* ($F= 0.551$, $df = 5$, 204 , $p = 0.737$), *B. erythrura* ($F= 0.548$, $df = 5$, 204 , $p = 0.740$), *A. amphitrite* ($F = 1.56$, $df = 5$, 204 , $p = 0.172$) and Others ($F= 0.34$, $df = 5$, 204 , $p = 0.888$) in the current study.

Highest and lowest population of Black Bean Aphids, incidence and severity was observed on interaction between negative control and dry season synthetic pesticide and interaction between wet seasons respectively (Table 4.4). Effectiveness of all combinations of pesticidal plants interacted with wet season was as similar as synthetic pesticide in both seasons on reduction of abundance of aphids, incidence and severity (Table 4.4). Contrary, the interaction between during dry season DT: DA: VA and combination of *D. trifoliata* and *V. amygdalina* (DT: VA) were the most effective against aphids. An interaction between combinations of DT: DA: VA was the most effective on reduction of incidence. In addition, all interaction between the combinations were effective against reduction of severity of aphids except combination of DA: VA which was less effective during dry season.

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Table 4.4: Effect of botanicals and season interaction on Abundance, incidence and severity of aphids and beneficial insects

Season*Treatments	Aphids abundance	Incidence abundance	Severity abundance	<i>C.albiceps</i>	<i>C.megacephala</i>	<i>S.africa</i>	<i>S.spilogaster</i>	<i>B.erythrura</i>	<i>A.amphitrite</i>	Others
Dry*control	33.94 ^a	77.78 ^a	1.67 ^a	0.61	0.89	0.61	1.000	0.28	1.11	1.33
Dry*DA:VA	21.83 ^b	51.11 ^b	1.33 ^b	0.33	0.39	0.56	0.611	0.17	0.72	1.17
Dry*DT:DA	16.07 ^{bc}	46.67 ^{bc}	1.00 ^c	0.11	0.11	0.44	0.500	0.11	0.67	1.06
Dry*DT:VA	12.94 ^{cd}	45.56 ^{bc}	0.94 ^c	0.11	0.11	0.39	0.444	0.11	0.56	0.83
Dry* DT:DA:VA	9.51 ^{cd}	37.78 ^{cd}	0.89 ^c	0.06	0.11	0.33	0.389	0.11	0.50	0.78
Wet*control	7.84 ^{de}	31.11 ^d	0.78 ^{cd}	0.06	0.06	0.22	0.389	0.06	0.50	0.72
Wet*DA:VA	1.98 ^{ef}	13.33 ^e	0.56 ^{de}	0.06	0.06	0.11	0.278	0.06	0.33	0.56
Wet*DT:DA	1.80 ^{ef}	11.11 ^e	0.39 ^{ef}	0.06	0.00	0.06	0.222	0.06	0.22	0.44
Wet*DT:VA	1.11 ^{ef}	7.78 ^e	0.28 ^{ef}	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.167	0.00	0.17	0.33
Wet*DT:DA:VA	0.50 ^f	5.56 ^e	0.28 ^{ef}	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.111	0.00	0.06	0.33
Wet*PC	0.22 ^f	4.44 ^e	0.22 ^f	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.056	0.00	0.00	0.28
Dry*PC	0.18 ^f	2.22 ^e	0.17 ^f	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00	0.22
SE	2.45	4.44	0.12	0.12	0.18	0.15	0.17	0.07	0.21	0.26
P.value	0.001	0.001	0.013	0.097	0.148	0.737	0.345	0.740	0.172	0.737

Different letters within the same column indicate significant difference at P= 0.05 as determined by Tukey's Test;

Dry season*(PC = Synthetic pesticide, NC = Negative control (Without treatment application), Dry season*(DT: DA: VA = Mixture of *Derris trifoliata*, *Dysphania ambrosioides* and *Vernonia amygdalina*, DT: DA = Mixture of *Derris trifoliata* and *Dysphania ambrosioides*, DT: VA = Mixture of *Derris trifoliata* and *Vernonia amygdalina*, DA: VA = Mixture of *Dysphania ambrosioides* and *Vernonia amygdalina*) each mixture 200g, SE = Standard error and P. value= Probability value. Wet season*(PC = Synthetic pesticide, NC = Negative control (Without application of any chemical), Wet season*(DT: DA: VA = Mixture of *Derris trifoliata*, *Dysphania ambrosioides* and *Vernonia amygdalina*, DT: DA = Mixture of *Derris trifoliata* and *Dysphania ambrosioides*, DT: VA = Mixture of *Derris trifoliata* and *Vernonia amygdalina*, DA: VA = Mixture of *Dysphania ambrosioides* and *Vernonia amygdalina*) each mixture 200g, SE = Standard error and P. value= Probability value.

4.5.6 Common bean yield

However, there was a significant effect ($F = 9.78$, $df = 5, 24$, $p = 0.0001$) of treatment (Table 4.5) and interaction ($F = 2.81$, $df = 5, 24$ and $p = 0.039$) between season and treatments on yield (Table 4.7). However, there was no significant effect ($F = 2.75$, $df = 5, 24$ and $p = 0.110$) of season on yield. The highest bean yield was noted on plots sprayed with synthetic pesticide while the lowest was on negative control (Table 4.5). Nevertheless, there was no significant difference in yield of common bean among pesticidal plant extract combinations.

Table 4.5: Common bean yield

Season	Yield
Wet	966.95
Dry	829.89
SE	58.44
LSD _{0.05}	170.582
P.value	0.110
Treatments	
PC	1457.18 ^a
DT:DA:VA	953.23 ^b
DA:VA	917.08 ^b
DT:DA	806.62 ^b
DT:VA	752.87 ^{bc}
NC	503.54 ^c
SE	101.23
P.value	0.0001

Different letters within the same column indicate significant difference at $P = 0.05$ as determined by Tukey's Test;

PC = Synthetic pesticide, NC = Negative control (Without treatment application), DT: DA: VA = Mixture of *Derris trifoliata*, *Dysphania ambrosioides* and *Vernonia amygdalina*, DT: DA = Mixture of *Derris trifoliata* and *Dysphania ambrosioides*, DT: VA = Mixture of *Derris trifoliata* and *Vernonia amygdalina*, DA: VA = Mixture of *Dysphania ambrosioides* and *Vernonia amygdalina*, SE = Standard error and P. value= Probability value.

The highest common bean yield was observed in plots sprayed with synthetic pesticide while the lowest yield was observed in plots with no pesticide application during wet season (Table 4.6). Comparatively, the highest bean yield was recorded on pesticidal plant extract mixture of *D. trifoliata*, *D. ambrosioides* and *V. amygdalina* (DT: DA: VA) during dry season. However, there was no statistical difference that was observed on bean yield between different mixtures of pesticidal plants both seasons.

Table 4.6: Common bean yield

Interaction	Means(kg/ha)	Groups		
Dry*Synthetic	1786.613	a		
Dry*DTDAVA	1150.210		b	
Wet*Synthetic	1127.750		b	
Wet*DTDA	955.250		b	c
Wet*DAVA	917.833		b	c d
Dry*DAVA	916.323		b	c d
Dry*DTVA	800.487		b	c d e
Wet*DTDAVA	756.250		b	c d e
Wet*DTVA	705.250		c	d e
Dry*DTDA	657.987		c	d e
Wet*CONTROL	517.000			d e
Dry*CONTROL	490.073			e
SE	143.16			
P.value	0.039			

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Different letters within the same column indicate significant difference at $P= 0.05$ as determined by Tukey's Test;

PC = Synthetic pesticide, NC = Negative control (Without treatment application), DT: DA: VA = Mixture of *Derris trifoliata*, *Dysphania ambrosioides* and *Vernonia amygdalina*, DT: DA = Mixture of *Derris trifoliata* and *Dysphania ambrosioides*, DT: VA = Mixture of *Derris trifoliata* and *Vernonia amygdalina*, DA: VA = Mixture of *Dysphania ambrosioides* and *Vernonia amygdalina*, SE = Standard error and P. value= Probability

4.6 Discussion

4.6.1 Pesticidal plants

The findings from the present study have revealed that pesticidal plants namely *D. Trifoliata* (DT), *D. ambrosioides* (DA) and *V. amygdalina* (VA) in combinations of DT: DA: VA, DT: DA, DT: VA and DA: VA have demonstrated to contain certain pesticidal activity against Black Bean Aphids (BBAs) when compared with negative control (Nothing was applied for the control of BBAs). According to Roy *et al.* (2016); Isman (2016); Green *et al.* (2017); Stevenson *et al.* (2017) reported that botanical plants contain biological activities against insect pests.

All the tested combinations from this study, revealed a varied efficacy against BBAs. A combinations of DT: DA: VA and DT: VA demonstrated great effect of insecticidal activity by reducing the abundance of BBAs and thereby minimizing incidence and severity of BBAs. This finding relate to Subedi *et al.* (2018) who reported that mixture of pesticidal plant species namely *Falconeria insignis*, *Agave americana*, *Acorus calamus*, *Nicotiana tabacum* and *Melia azedarach* were effective in controlling Bean Aphid population. In addition, Kummar *et al.* (2007) reported high effectiveness of combination of *Azadirachta indica* and *Millettia pinnata* were effective against aphids and mites. Furthermore, Pavela and Benelli (2016) argued that mixture of terpenes from different plant species they play an important role in plant defense against a range of organisms.

Recent studies have also revealed that improved penetration of a given terpene with another less toxic terpene may result in a synergic combination against crop insect pests (Tak and Isman, 2017). Isman (2014) reported that mixing of pesticidal plants could improve its efficacy by reducing chemical breakdown and increasing persistent. Similar findings have been reported by Cloyd (2009); Ahmad (2009); Ramzan *et al.* (2019) who reported that mixture of different synthetic pesticide increased its effectiveness by increasing wide range of insect pests.

The chemical compounds extracts from these individual pesticidal plants in combined form could contribute to the synergy effect against reduction of abundance BBAs. The extracts from leaves of *V. amygdalina* has proven to have active ingredient of vernolide and vernadol, epivernodalol which have repelling and deterrent effect against BBAs (Green *et al.*, 2017; Mkenda *et al.*, 2015; Tembo *et al.*, 2018). Leaf extract from *D. ambrosioides* has proven to contain pesticidal activities as documented by other researcher. Pavela *et al.* (2017) reported that *D. ambrosioides* contains phytochemical compounds such as flavonoids, saponins, terpenes, sterols, and alkaloids which are anti-feedant and discourage insects from eating crops. On other hand, *D. trifoliata* also has proven to have pesticidal activity against insect pest. El - Wakeil (2013) reported that *Derris. trifoliata* is one of the broad spectrum pesticidal plant which contains active ingredient known as rotenone that acts as a contact and stomach poison, kills various insect pests on crops. However, synthetic pesticide was the most effective in reducing abundance of BBAs in this study by exhibiting least Incidence and Severity to the bean crop. The higher effectiveness of synthetic pesticide was due to persistent which can take more than two weeks and quick acting against insect pests due to its active ingredient (Biondi *et al.*, 2012).

Interestingly, the lowest incidence and severity of BBAs during both wet and dry season was observed in plots treated with combinations of all the three pesticidal plants namely *D. Trifoliata*, *D. ambrosioides* and *V. amygdalina* (DT: DA: VA) with concentration of 200 g/L each. This could be attributed by the effectiveness of these pesticidal plants secondary metabolites which have anti- feedant, repellent, contact

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and gut poison of crop insect pests as reported by Matsuura *et al.* (2016). Other factor which contributed to low abundance of BBAs during wet season is plant growth stage, frequency and heavy rainfall which could keep down the population of BBAs as opposed to dry season due to absence of rainfall when most of aphids are prevalent as reported by Leather *et al.* (2017); Feng *et al.* (1992); Honek and Martinkova, (2004).

4.6.2 Bean yield

Higher beans yield observed in IMIDA C344SE (Cypermethrin 144 g/L + Imidacloprid 200 g/L) was the signal of low Incidence and Severity caused by BBAs compared with other pesticidal plants similar to the results as reported by (Mkenda *et al.*, 2015). Pesticidal plant combinations of *Derris trifoliata*, *Dysphania ambrosioides* and *Vernonia amygdalina* revealed to have high common bean yield compared to the rest of combinations which could be contributed by combination of different chemical compounds resulted into high protective effect against BBAs. Results showed that severe attack of BBAs was critical during vegetating, flowering and podding stage of crop growth that could probably have contributed to common bean yield variations (Nyirenda *et al.*, 2010). The results also revealed that among other flies, *C. albiceps* was the only fly recorded to have significant effect on bean yield. Probably this fly could have an influence on increase on yield as it was observed as the main flower visitor during the entire study period. This result is in agreement with the findings by Douka *et al.* (2018) who reported that flower visitor insects resulted into great bean yield.

4.6.3 Conclusion and Recommendations

Findings from this research shows that pesticidal plant extracts from a combination of *D. Trifoliata*, *D. ambrosioides* and *V. amygdalina* have demonstrated great effectiveness against BBAs and reduce levels of abundance, Incidence and Severity of aphids. Other combinations during wet season were as effective as synthetic pesticide against BBAs. Similarly, pesticidal plants also with all three combinations resulted into a high common bean yield during study season. Therefore, a combination of study pesticidal plant extracts could be used as an alternative to control insect pests for small scale farmers in Tanzania.

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